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Information Needs and Seeking Behaviour by the Students of Humanities and Social Science in Bhagat Phool Singh Mahila Vishwavidyalaya, Sonipat, Haryana: An Analysis Study

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Abstract

The study aims to know the information needs and seeking behaviour of students in Humanities and Social Science at Bhagat Phool Singh Mahila Vishwavidyalaya, Sonipat, Haryana. 226 (74.83%) students give a proper reply out of them, and 110 (48.67%) of the 1st year student give a proper reply. 191 (84.51%) of the respondents are using e-resources for information-seeking. Information daily 94 (41.59%) of the respondents are highly used to seeking information

Keywords Information Needs, Information Seeking Behaviour, E-Resources, Information Resources, Humanities Students & Social Science, Databases

Introduction

Bhagat Phool Singh Mahila Vishwavidyalaya (BPSMV) was started in 1936 to empower girls through education. This is the 1st Women University in North India, which provides education to KG to Ph.D. students in various subjects, i.e., English, Management, Laws, Economics, Social Work, Education, Computer Science, Fashion Technology, Hotel Management, Commerce, Food Nutrition, and Engineering, in rural areas.

Objective of study

1. To determine the information needs and information-seeking behaviour of the students of humanities and social science.
2. To explore information needs and seeking behaviours
3. To know the students attitude toward information seeking
4. To know the usefulness of e-resources for information seeking
5. To know the problems faced by humanities and social science students
6. To know the satisfaction level of students

Information Needs: The study acknowledges that research depends on information needs. Hertzum and Pejtersen (2000) describe information explosion as the time involved in obtaining information in effective ways by "seeking both oral and written communication." According to Noble and Coughlin (1997), the study shows that 85% of the respondents used print journals, 99% used computers, 89% used software, 87% connected with campus networks, 73% used electronic information technology, and 35% "lacked training in how to access e-resources." The Kumar (1968) survey was conducted at Delhi University, Department of Chemistry, by researchers, scholars, and teachers. The finding shows that 71% need to improve their skills in services and do not use the library as much. Respondents used current information for their study.

Information Seeking Behavior: Based on the explanation, the study considered information seeking behaviour. Dunn (1986) This study addresses the psychological motivation for "information seeking behaviour of undergraduate students" and psychological needs in the area of research. Wilson (1981) developed the information-seeking behavior concept based on motivation theories by Maslow, Hergberg, and McGregor. Seth and Parida (2006) found that information seeking begins with quality education, which depends on planning, programs, and resources. The people has lack knowledge about information access, awareness, and motivation. Fidzani (1998), "Information-seeking behavior of graduate students at the University of Botswana," notes that textbooks and periodicals are popular sources of information

Review of Literature

Information seeking by students of the humanities and social sciences, understanding changing needs. Nicholas et al. (2009) mentioned the above in this study. Undergraduate students can access databases in the library. "Information needs and seeking behavior associated with students and differences between them and other academic communities" and, in some cases, for practitioners. The social networking sites and blogs will shape students information-seeking behavior. George et al.'s (2006) study found that undergraduate students often meet with teachers who guide direction and provide resources. The Internet plays a vital role, but students use print resources. Prekop's (2002) study "found that the information needs and seeking behavior" literature considers individual seeker performance. The study explicitly considers "information needs and information seeking" from a collaborative perspective. Farrell and Bates (2009) study described the "information needs and seeking behavior of LIS students." Information resources, e-mail, e-journals, websites, electronic media, and communication problems were reported. The students have group projects, sharing information resources, teamwork skills, group understanding, and skill development. Kerins, Madden, and Fulton (1970) presented various research methods in sufficient detail on the "information-seeking behavior of engineering and law students in Ireland."

Analysis

The study considered the eight departments of students, i.e., the Department of Political Science, Department of History, Department of Geography, Department of Social Work, Department of English, Department of Physical Education, Department of Education, and Department of Management Studies. In humanities and social sciences this study was done to know the information needs and seeking behaviour of humanities and social sciences students in Bhagat Phool Singh Mahila Vishwavidyalaya, Sonipat, Haryana.

Result and Discussion

Table -1
Department wise Responses to the Questionnaire Distribution

Department wise responses	Political Science	History	Geography	Social Work	English	Phy. Education	Education	Management	Total
Questionnaire distribution	36	38	44	34	32	46	38	34	302
Reponses	30	28	32	24	26	32	28	26	226
Total	83.33%	73.68%	72.72%	70.59%	81.25%	69.57%	73.68%	76.47%	74.83%

Table 1 revealed that 226 (74.83%) respondents were given a reply, while 83.33% were from the Department of Political Science, 73.68% were from the Department of History, 72.72% were from the Department of Geography, 70.59% were from the Department of Social Work, 81.25% were from the Department of English, 69.57% were from the Department of Physical Education, 73.68% were from the Department of Education, and 76.47% were from the Department of Management.

Table-2
Year-wise Demographic Characteristics

Year-wise	Political Science	History	Geography	Social Work	English	Phy. Education	Education	Management	Total
1 st Year	16	12	16	10	14	18	10	14	110 (48.67%)
2 nd Year	6	10	12	6	8	10	12	6	70 (30.97%)
3 rd Year	8	6	4	8	4	4	6	6	46 (20.35%)
Total	30	28	32	24	26	32	28	26	226 (100%)

Table 2 revealed that 110 (48.67%) of the 1st year students gave replies, 70 (30.97%) of the 2nd year students gave replies, and only 46 (20.35%) of the 3rd year students gave

reply. The overall majority of the first year students gave a proper reply.

Table-3
Use of E-Resources for Information Seeking

Use of E-Resources	Political Science	History	Geography	Social Work	English	Phy. Education	Education	Management	Total
Yes	27	24	26	19	24	26	22	23	191 (84.51%)
No	3	4	6	5	2	6	6	3	35 (15.49%)
Total	30	28	32	24	26	32	28	26	226 (100%)

Table 3 reveals that undergraduate students are using information to e-resources 191 (84.51%), and 35 (15.49%) of the respondents are not using e-resources for information seeking. The majority of respondents are using e-resources for information seeking

Table-4
Frequency of Information Seeking

Frequency	Political Science	History	Geography	Social Work	English	Phy. Education	Education	Management	Total
Daily	14	10	12	6	8	18	14	12	94 (41.59%)
2-3 times in week	5	6	8	12	9	5	6	4	55 (24.34%)
Weekly	4	8	4	2	3	4	8	6	39 (17.26%)
Monthly	5	4	6	3	6	2	0	3	29 (12.83%)
Rarely	2	0	2	1	0	3	0	1	9 (3.98%)
Total	30	28	32	24	26	32	28	26	226 (100%)

Table 4 indicates that 94 (41.59%) of the respondents are using information daily for information seeking. The following were 55 (24.34%) of the respondents using information 2-3 times a week for information seeking; 39 (17.26%) of the respondents are using information weekly; 29 (12.83%) of the respondents are using information monthly; and only 9 (3.98%) of the respondents are using information rarely for information seeking.

Table-5
Frequency of using of E-Resources for Information Seeking

Location	Political Science	History	Geography	Social Work	English	Phy. Education	Education	Management	Total
Library	15	14	12	10	6	13	12	11	93 (41.15%)
Home	8	6	4	6	8	7	7	9	55 (24.34%)
Cafeteria	5	4	14	4	7	5	6	4	49 (21.68%)
Other	2	4	2	4	5	7	3	2	29 (12.83%)
Total	30	28	32	24	26	32	28	26	226 (100%)

The table-5 analysis shows that 93 (41.15%) of the students are frequently using libraries for e-resources for information seeking, 55 (24.34%) of the students are using homes for e-resources, 49 (21.68%) of the students are using cafeterias for e-resources, and 29 (12.83%) of the students are using other locations for information seeking.

Table-6
Purpose of Information Seeking

Place to Access Information	Political Science	History	Geography	Social Work	English	Phy. Education	Education	Management	Total
Education	10	13	18	6	8	22	14	11	102 (45.13%)
Home work	12	5	6	9	5	2	6	8	53 (23.45%)
Update Knowledge	6	6	4	3	6	2	7	5	39 (17.26%)
Exam. preparation	2	4	4	6	7	6	1	2	32 (14.16%)
Total	30	28	32	24	26	32	28	26	226 (100%)

Table 6 shows that 102 (45.13%) of the users are using information for educational purposes for information seeking, 53 (23.45%) of the users are using information for home work, 39 (17.26%) of the users are using information to update knowledge, and only 32 (14.16%) of the users are using information for exam preparation for information seeking.

Table-7
Most useful Search Engine for Information Seeking

Search Engine	Political Science	History	Geography	Social Work	English	Phy. Education	Education	Management	Total
Google	22	20	12	10	8	12	8	14	106 (46.90%)
Face Book	2	4	10	6	8	4	6	5	45 (19.91%)
Yahoo	4	2	2	4	3	7	4	3	29 (12.83%)
Twitter	2	2	4	2	2	7	4	2	25 (11.06%)
Others	0	0	4	2	5	2	6	2	21 (9.29%)
Total	30	28	32	24	26	32	28	26	226 (100%)

Table 7 shows that 106 (46.90%) of the users frequently use Google search engines for information seeking, followed by 45 (19.91%) of the respondents using Facebook, 29 (12.83%) of the students using Yahoo, 25 (11.06%) using Twitter, and a few of them 21(9.29%) using other search engines for information seeking

Table-8
Problem faced in Meeting the Information Needs

Problem Face	Political Science	History	Geography	Social Work	English	Phy. Education	Education	Management	Total
Slow Access Speed	5	9	13	6	4	11	6	13	67 (29.65%)
Downloading Problem	7	7	6	7	10	5	7	6	55 (24.34%)
Unwanted Information	8	5	2	8	6	4	3	4	40 (17.70%)
Lack of Quality Information	8	4	7	2	4	6	5	1	37 (16.37%)
Connectivity Problem	2	3	4	1	2	6	7	2	27 (11.95%)
Total	30	28	32	24	26	32	28	26	226 (100%)

Table 8 indicates that 67 (29.65%) of the respondents view the problem as due to slow access speed in meeting the information needs, followed by 55 (24.34%) who found a downloading problem, 40 (17.70%) who found unwanted information, 37 (16.37%) who found a lack of quality information, and only 27 (11.95%) who found a connectivity problem in meeting the information needs

Table-9
Use fullness of E-Resources for Information Seeking

Usefulness	Political Science	History	Geography	Social Work	English	Phy. Education	Education	Management	Total
Very Useful	19	12	15	8	15	11	9	12	101 (44.69%)
Less Useful	4	6	7	5	7	9	11	4	53 (23.45%)
No Useful	2	3	4	3	1	5	3	5	26 (11.50%)
Rarely useful	5	7	6	8	3	7	5	5	46 (20.35%)
Total	30	28	32	24	26	32	28	26	226 (100%)

Table 9 revealed that 101 (44.69%) of the respondents view e-resources as very useful for information seeking, 53 (23.45%) of the respondents say they are less useful for information seeking, 26 (11.50%) of the respondents view them as no useful, and only 46 (20.35%) of the respondents view them as rarely useful for information seeking.

Table-10
Satisfaction Level of Information Seeking

Satisfaction level	Political Science	History	Geography	Social Work	English	Phy. Education	Education	Management	Total
Fully Satisfied	17	16	18	14	15	18	16	15	129 (57.08%)
Least Satisfied	9	6	12	7	6	6	6	5	57 (25.22%)
Partially Satisfied	3	4	1	3	3	4	3	4	25 (11.06%)
Dissatisfied	1	2	1	0	2	4	3	2	15 (6.64%)
Total	30	28	32	24	26	32	28	26	226 (100%)

According to the table-10 analysis, 129 (57.08%) of the users were fully satisfied with information seeking, 57 (25.22%) of the users were least satisfied, 25 (11.06%) of the users were partially satisfied, and a few of them, 15 (6.64%), were dissatisfied with information seeking

Conclusion

Today, information needs and seeking behavior are very powerful tools for students. 93 (41.15%) of the users frequently use e-resources in the library and 55 (24.34%) at home. Knowing the needs and seeking behavior of students' humanities and social science. That is 102 (45.13%) for education and 53 (23.45%) for home work. The most useful search engine is Google 106 (46.90%). The problem faced by the users in accessing the information is 67 (29.65%) slow internet speed. 101 (44.69%) is very useful for e-resources. More than 57% of users are fully satisfied with library resources.

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